

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D5.4

RECORDED SUMEX WEBINARS AND VIDEOS

Summary:

This document describes audiovisual results of the SUMEX project. In addition, the document includes the content description of storytelling videos and videos for the 5 focus areas, which highlight different aspects of the project.

Authors:

Andreas Endl, Vienna University of Economics and Business, Senior Research Fellow and Project Manager

Mariana Kovacic-Lukic, Vienna University of Economics and Business, Project Staff Member

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	BACKGROUND.....	4
1.1	OBJECTIVES AND IMPACT	4
1.2	DESIGN AND PRODUCTION.....	4
1.3	DISSEMINATION.....	5
2	SUMEX VIDEOS.....	6
2.1	SUMEX PROJECT INTRODUCTION VIDEO: SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT IN THE EXTRACTIVE INDUSTRIES.....	6
2.2	SUMEX MOOC ONLINE COURSE INTRODUCTION VIDEO: SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT IN THE EXTRACTIVE INDUSTRY	8
2.3	INTRODUCTION TO SUMEX FOCUS AREA 1: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL IMPACTS	10
2.4	INTRODUCTION TO SUMEX FOCUS AREA 2: LAND USE PLANNING.....	11
2.5	INTRODUCTION TO SUMEX FOCUS AREA 3: HEALTH & SAFETY.....	13
2.6	INTRODUCTION TO SUMEX FOCUS AREA 4: PERMITTING	14
2.7	INTRODUCTION TO SUMEX FOCUS AREA 5: REPORTING.....	16
2.8	AV STORYTELLING 3	17

1 BACKGROUND

1.1 OBJECTIVES AND IMPACT

The aim of the EU project SUMEX (Sustainable Management in Extractive industries) is to foster sustainability in the extractive sector by analysing existing frameworks, providing good sustainable practice cases, and establishing a [SUMEX sustainability framework](#) focused on extractive industries in Europe. One way of achieving this goal is the development of training materials and creating a community of practice. Audio-visual storytelling was chosen as one method to disseminate the project results.

The topics of the videos include:

- a. **Audiovisual storytelling number 1** – introduction to the SUMEX project by the project coordinator: Michael Tost (Montanuniversität Leoben) presents the project's background, the SUMEX objectives, and the anticipated results.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3YOMNvOfCX4>
- b. **Audiovisual storytelling number 2** – introduction to the MOOC: In this video, André Martinuzzi (Vienna University of Economics and Business) introduces the online course, i.e. course format, focus areas and the respective experts.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1LZSolFrLdI>
- c. A presentation of the **five SUMEX focus areas**:
The presented areas are impact assessment, land use planning, health and safety, permitting, and reporting. The videos have been utilised for the [Massive Online Open Course](#) (MOOC), and to illustrate the state of the art (e.g. outlining the current problem setting, EU and national policy and common business practice, as well as innovative solutions for extractive operation in or near nature-protected areas), and European challenges in the extractive industries.

This document presents the background information, design, and the audio transcripts of the seven videos. In addition to the seven presented videos, five expert talks were produced, one for each focus area. The videos are part of WP4 and core elements of the MOOC developed in 2022. The first live run of the course started on 7.11.2022 and ran until 18.12.2022. The third storytelling video will be created in the upcoming months as part of the second live run of the MOOC. During the two live runs, the course is available for all registered members of the FutureLearn platform. Outside of the live runs, the course is available for paying members only which is why the videos on the focus areas are not publicly available. In chapter 2, the transcripts of the produced videos are presented.

1.2 DESIGN AND PRODUCTION

During the design and production of the videos, the following aspects were considered:

- a. The visual design should correspond to the project colors and design. These consist of pastel colors and the background including a visualization of an extraction site, a wind turbine symbolizing environmental sustainability and houses for the local communities.
- b. The focus area videos should be told by real people to create a stronger and more professional base for the provided information. An expert from the respective field presents the respective focus area. These experts are Pamela Lesser (impact assessment), Katharina Gugerell (land use planning), Michael Tost (health & safety), Andreas Endl (permitting), and Anders Forsgren (reporting). The experts have backgrounds in research and academia, as well as industry. For the project introduction, Michael Tost

was chosen as representative in his role as Professor for Sustainable Mining Technology at Montanuniversität Leoben and project coordinator. For the introduction to the MOOC, André Martinuzzi was chosen as representative in his role as Head of the Institute for Managing Sustainability at the Vienna University of Economics and Business (WUW).

- c. WUW was responsible for the development of video storyboards in cooperation with the respective focus area experts. The five focus area videos for the MOOC were kept to two to four minutes as they are used for introducing the respective topic. The other two storytelling-videos are a little longer with six to eight minutes. This enables the provision of enough information while not overloading the viewers and keeping them interested. The videos aim to create awareness for the project, respectively for the MOOC and link to the project for further information.
- d. The texts were editorially revised by an English native speaker. In the videos, a language, terminology and a narrative style were chosen that are common in the extractive sector and correspond to the viewing habits and experiences of the primary target groups policymakers, industry and civil society. Furthermore, particular care was taken not to use any scientific jargon to present the content of the videos in an easily understandable way.
- e. The production of the videos included the following steps: Creation of the off-text considering the above-mentioned points and interview-questions (storyboard including directing instructions), recording of video and audio in a professional Greenbox Studio, rough cut, animation of the background, selection of background music that fits the respective story and message conveyed, and detailed realization.
- f. Multiple feedback loops were conducted with the respective focus area experts to ensure involvement and investment in the process and the later dissemination.

1.3 DISSEMINATION

The dissemination for the videos includes the following activities:

- a. Integration of the focus area videos and the video introducing the course into the MOOC. The first live run of the online course had 423 learners registered (as of 7 March 2023). For the second live run an increase in registrations is anticipated due to increased promotion in the run up to the start date as well as recent EU raw material policy developments (draft EU Critical Raw Material Act Proposal on March 16, 2023).
- b. In the run-up to the second live run of the MOOC, news snippets will be created promoting the course and the videos every two weeks in the framework of a newsletter. In addition, MOOC participants will be asked to give testimonials on the course. Furthermore, a LinkedIn event will be set up to connect with interested learners on social media.
- c. Extracts of the videos (in form of short clips) will be produced for social media for the promotion of the second MOOC live run.
- d. The two storytelling videos are available on YouTube and were promoted through social media campaigns in 2022 on Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook.
- e. Excerpts from the storytelling videos as well as the aforementioned expert talks will be used in the production of the SUMEX podcast planned for the upcoming months. More information will follow in Deliverable D5.5 Complementary capacity building material, which will be finalized by the end of April 2023.

2 SUMEX VIDEOS

Chapter 2 presents the videos of the project introduction (storytelling video no. 1), the MOOC introduction (storytelling video no. 2) as well as the video transcripts of the five focus areas. A third storytelling video is currently in preparation and will be published in connection with the second live run of the MOOC in August 2023.

2.1 SUMEX PROJECT INTRODUCTION VIDEO: SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT IN THE EXTRACTIVE INDUSTRIES

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3YOMNvOfCX4>

The history of humankind is inextricably linked to the history of mining. Copper, iron, salt and silver have been extracted from the earth by people for thousands of years and have contributed to the rise of cultures and societal progress.

Industrialization and technological progress would not have been possible without mining. Mineral resources have made people, companies, and entire regions wealthy, and mining was an important employer for a long time.

But mining can be tough and dangerous. Collapses, floods, and explosions cost many lives every year. Mining also damages the environment. Vegetation is cleared, rivers and groundwater are polluted, and entire ecosystems get destroyed to make way for mines. As a result, social acceptance for mining has fallen throughout Europe over recent decades and new mines are rarely opened.

But this does not solve the problem, because Europe imports minerals on a large scale from countries with lower social and environmental standards. This trend is set to continue because Europe's demand for resources such as copper, cobalt, nickel, and lithium are rising continuously. They are needed for electronic products from mobile phones to e-bikes, wind turbines and electric cars. The switch from combustion engines to electric motors, which is urgently needed to mitigate climate change, requires electronics, charging stations and batteries and therefore minerals that are hardly mined in Europe. Europe is therefore dependent on imports

that are not always secured. This has been clearly demonstrated by the supply chain disruptions associated with the COVID pandemic.

Europe needs responsible and sustainable extraction. This is the only way to guarantee high social and environmental standards and at the same time reduce dependency on imports. This is exactly where SUMEX, the EU project I am leading, starts. Since the end of 2020, I've been working with 10 major organizations including universities, companies, and public administration.

Our first step is to investigate projects across Europe whether EU funded national or industrial that deal with aspects of responsible and sustainable extraction. For the first time, a data set of several hundred projects will be collected and we will show what is already possible today. Then we will analyse the collected projects using a standardized catalogue.

We cover five focus areas:

- 1) permitting: in other words, the granting of extraction licenses;
- 2) land use planning: how mining and other forms of land use interact with each other;
- 3) health and safety: here we address how to avoid risks to workers and local communities;
- 4) reporting, which is about how the impacts and risks of extraction activities become transparent;
- 5) and social and environmental impact assessments, which help to identify and reduce risks and impacts on people and the environment.

On this basis, we will identify how narrow or deep the impulses for a transformation towards sustainable and responsible extraction practices in Europe are. Following this approach, we will select and describe good practice cases that can easily be replicated in other locations. By demonstrating sound, responsible, and sustainable extraction practices, the SUMEX project creates a scheme of reference for governments, administrations, and approval procedures.

Through targeted dissemination, networking, and community building, SUMEX contributes to the transformation of the entire extraction sector in Europe.

For industry, this brings two advantages:

- 1) EU right transparency on good practices shows which requirements can be expected in future licensing procedures.
- 2) At the same time, social acceptance of new projects and the extraction sector in general will be increased.

Citizens in Europe benefit from SUMEX as the project helps to ensure that sustainability and responsibility are practiced in the extractive sectors, that problems are no longer shifted to developing countries, and that Europe's dependency on imports is reduced.

We're constantly discovering new examples of how extraction can be practiced in an innovative and responsible way. If you would like to be part of the change too or you are interested in our project results, please visit our website at www.sumexproject.eu

2.2 SUMEX MOOC ONLINE COURSE INTRODUCTION VIDEO: SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT IN THE EXTRACTIVE INDUSTRY

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1LZSolFrLdI>

AM: Minerals are crucial for many industries. For green technologies, we need for instance silicon, lithium, and a broad range of rare earth elements.

The construction sector needs gravel, and sand, and dimensional stones. And the manufacturing industry needs metals like aluminium, steel, and copper. The demand for all of these minerals will be skyrocketing in the coming years and future productivity, prosperity, and jobs depend on them.

At the same time, Europe is highly dependent on the imports of minerals from countries with low environmental and social standards. For sustainable and responsible business conduct, it is essential that these minerals are not extracted on the expense of the environment and people. We need a truly sustainable form of extraction which minimizes its ecological footprint and safeguards its social license to operate.

This transition to sustainable extraction is challenging for both policy and industry. While European policy has set ambitious environmental standards, the implementation varies substantially in the different European member states, which is particularly difficult for multinational companies. Facing these policy demands and raising societal concerns, companies need to change their business practices.

Potential solutions include new ways to value ecosystems and biodiversity, proactive resolutions of land use conflicts, and innovative ways for local communities' approval and trust.

In SUMEX, a 3 year project funded by the European Commission, we dealt with all of these issues. We aim at establishing a sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe involving civil society, academia, industry, and governments.

One of the key outputs of this project is an online course which provides you with a multitude of insights, tools, and contacts to outstanding experts from all around Europe. Together we will address key challenges for industry and policy in the transition to sustainable extraction, we will examine how state-of-the-art sustainability concepts can be implemented at the operational level, and we will outline potential solutions based on practical examples which can be applied across Europe.

The course is divided into several weeks.

In the first week of the course, we will explore why sustainable extraction is important and what the underlying concepts are.

In the second week we will highlight how to assess the impacts of an extractive project. Pamela Lesser is our expert for this topic. She has been researching sustainable mining for more than a decade and has been working with impact assessment for 25 years.

PM: So, impact assessment is a planning management tool that is intended to evaluate the environmental and social impacts of a project. Where impact assessment is now if we are looking at the European context, it really does just evaluate the environmental impact of a project and it does so in fairly traditional ways. Where it should go? It should broaden that scope to include social and economic impacts but also give those affected stakeholders a voice earlier in the process.

AM: In the third week, you will learn how to solve tension between extractive activities and other forms of land use. Katharina Gugerell is an expert of sustainable land use and sustainability transformations and will provide you with valuable insights.

KG: I think the main objective of land use planning is to provide the just access to resources. That means that we are balancing different private and public interests and that we are trying to appropriate those interests in the land use and to find a spatial appropriation that on the one hand is providing those different goods and services, but on the other hand does not exceed planetary boundaries and does not overstretch the carrying capacity of ecosystems.

AM: In week four, we will put the spotlight on health and safety. Michael Tost has worked in this area for many years at Rio Tinto, one of the largest mining companies in the world. He is now professor for sustainable mining technology at Montanuniversität Leoben and coordinator of the SUMEX project.

MT: Mining in itself is dangerous. Therefore, health and safety is important. And in order to deal with those hazards, the danger in the mining environment, we need to establish a goal of zero harm. Nobody should get injured. No worker, the communities, the neighbours, nor the environment should actually be negatively impacted by a mining operation.

AM: In week five, we will address the challenge of licensing new extractive projects while conserving biodiversity. Andreas Endl has a background in human ecology and has worked over the last 10 years with policymakers in Europe on establishing sustainable development in the extractive sector.

AE: For companies, the main challenge is to take into account in their permit the nearby nature protected areas conservation objectives. And for the operational phase later of course to signify, to take into account during the permitting phase, to do rehabilitation, as well as exploitation at the very same time. For public authorities, it is to have resources and capacity at hand to effectively assess the permit so that it lives up to the legal provisions needed as well as to do this in a very short period of time to account for companies' actions.

AM: The last week of our online course provides insights on how to report sustainability performance of extraction companies considering transparency, trust, and effectiveness. Our high-level expert is Anders Forsgren who is working at Boliden, a high-tech metal company with mines and smelters all over Scandinavia.

AF: Sustainability reporting is crucial for companies in the extractive industry. One challenge is that we have a lot of different types of standards, different types of metrics, and it's really difficult to evaluate which one to

report on. And for some of these news focus areas like climate and biodiversity for example, there are no really well established metrics.

AM: By attending the course you will gain many benefits. As an industry representative you will learn how leading companies deal with the transition towards sustainable extraction. You will have a profound overview on new developments in legislation and regulatory tools, and you will know effective solutions.

As a member of public administration, you will be able to identify similarities and differences in implementing European standards in the member states and you will know how certain policies, strategies and concepts are perceived by those who are affected.

As young researchers, this course will help you to understand the key elements and concepts of sustainable extraction and the scientific discourse associated with it. You will also learn how sustainable extraction is put into practice by policymakers and industry.

So, register now and enrol in this course. Find out more on our website: www.sumexproject.eu

2.3 INTRODUCTION TO SUMEX FOCUS AREA 1: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL IMPACTS

Welcome to Week 2 of your course on sustainable management of mineral resource extraction.

I am Pamela Lesser and have been researching responsible mining for 10 years, and environmental and social impact assessment globally for over 25 years.

Last week we provided a general introduction to the course and gave an outlook onto the different topics that will be focused on in the coming weeks.

This week we will discover how the environmental and social impacts of an extractive project are identified and how the process as a whole informs decision making and contributes to sustainable development.

Indeed, various forms of mandatory impact assessments are implemented in over 182 countries around the world. It is applicable to any large-scale project, including extractive projects, and through its consultation requirements involves all interested stakeholders. These include policy makers, mining companies, local communities, and civil society organizations.

SUMEX recognizes Impact Assessment as a crucial part of sustainability management. However, the project recommends specific improvements along several lines:

- Meaningful engagement with all affected actors
- More rigorous analysis of social impacts
- Applying IA to closure and not only the initial permitting process of the extractive project

Against this background, this week we will discover:

- What are the major challenges industry and policymakers face to improve Impact Assessments effectiveness and thereby to promote sustainability?
- What are natural and social capital - and how can they be integrated into impact assessments?
- How to arrive at a more holistic approach that includes social impacts and that considers immediate and long-term impacts?

So, in this week

- 1) We will answer these questions with selected readings on major results of our SUMEX project including the SUMEX sustainability aspects and methodological framework discussed in week 1.
- 2) You will have the opportunity to hear insights from high-level experts in an interview-discussion.
- 3) We will showcase existing practices to make the content of the week more tangible and concrete.
- 4) And you will deepen your knowledge in a small exercise.

So, let's get started.

2.4 INTRODUCTION TO SUMEX FOCUS AREA 2: LAND USE PLANNING

Welcome to Week 3 of your course on sustainable management of mineral resource extraction.

My name is Katharina Gugerell, I am a land use planner and I do research on different topics in the broader field of sustainable land use, sustainability transformations, and how different actors, rights- and titleholders can successfully collaborate to co-create adequate solutions for so-called wicked planning problems and policy issues.

After discussing the concept of Impact Assessment last week, this week we will put the spotlight on Land Use Planning – and examine why it is important for sustainable extraction.

Next to water and energy, land is an important resource for extractive activities. In Europe in particular, competitions for various land use forms are high. Due to its limited availability, it is subject to various human development pressures, not only from the extractive sector, but also from housing or industrial activity.

It is the role of Land Use Planning to regulate this competition in an efficient, sustainable, and ethical manner. It identifies competing interests, expresses their implications, and assigns a land use in a way that promotes sustainability.

During the active phase of mineral extraction, Land Use Planning addresses benefits and trade-offs resulting from different land uses and land use practices. In some cases, conflicts resulting from different uses, are more effectively managed by affected stakeholders themselves. Take for example, extractive activity and reindeer herding that uses the nearby land for grazing but also which intersects transportation routes. For both, companies and reindeer herding communities it is important to find ways to identify conflicts and establish ways to manage collectively.

In particular, looking beyond the actual phase of mineral extraction is important since it is often neglected in the area of mineral extraction and public policy. This includes the use beyond the extractive life cycle as well as the safeguarding of mineral resources from other irreversible forms of land use.

At the end of this week, you will:

- understand the role of Land Use Planning in regulating competition amongst extractive activities and other land use forms;
- have an overview of land policy instruments supporting sustainable land use planning in the realm of extractive activities;
- And you will be able to critically assess the challenges of Land Use Planning and mining policy integration and identify possible mitigation strategies.

This week we have prepared background materials for you, interesting case study reports and expert statements. We will again organize an interview-discussion with high-level experts. And finally, you will test your knowledge in a small exercise.

Let's dive into it.

2.5 INTRODUCTION TO SUMEX FOCUS AREA 3: HEALTH & SAFETY

Welcome to Week 4 of your course on sustainable management of mineral resource extraction.

I am Michael Tost and I have worked in various health and safety positions at Rio Tinto, one of the largest mining companies in the world, in Austria and Canada for over 10 years, and I am now Professor for Sustainable Mining Technology at Montanuniversität Leoben. I have been teaching occupational health and safety courses over the last years and in my new role, Health and Safety plays an integral part as well, we want to make sites safer for example, with safe deep underground mining being a strategic priority. I have also been involved with a number of sustainability related EU projects in recent years and I am coordinator of the SUMEX project.

In the last weeks, we have provided you with insights into Impact Assessment and Land Use Planning. As you have seen in the weekly structure, this week we will focus on Health and Safety.

In an industry as dangerous as the extractive sector, adequate Health & Safety measures are of utmost importance to protect workers, communities, and the environment from harm. Several mining related disasters with catastrophic consequences for humans and the environment in the last years have led to increased pressure by civil society organisations and policymakers to improve Health & Safety standards. In addition, the global trend of improving working conditions and eliminating risks, has made Health & Safety management a higher priority for extractive operations.

So, what do we mean when we talk about risks? Risk is understood as a combination of the severity of damage and probability of its occurrence. These risks can come from a variety of sources, such as human behaviour and operational processes.

The aim of Health and Safety is to identify these risks and reduce the probability of them occurring. An effective way to reduce these risks is to put in place thorough company-wide risk management systems. Overall, Health and Safety regulations are one of the key instruments to ensure social and societal responsibility.

Given this importance, Health and Safety is one of the five focus areas within the overall framework of sustainability within the SUMEX project.

So, in this week of your course:

- we will give an overview of the key Health and Safety risks for workers, the local community and also link to the environment;
- we will highlight how we can protect people and the environment from harm, and;
- we will discuss state-of-the-art industry approaches for risk management, such as international standards and internal systems that companies are using.

So, let's start with the first activity.

2.6 INTRODUCTION TO SUMEX FOCUS AREA 4: PERMITTING

Welcome to Week 5 of your online course.

I am Andreas Endl and over the last 10 years I have been working with European Member State and European Commission policymakers on improving public policy and sustainable development in the extractive sector.

Last week, we heard from Michael about how companies address Health and Safety. While Health and Safety are especially important for already operating sites, developing new projects requires a company to adequately design and a public authority to effectively assess the new projects.

Therefore, this week, we will discover how companies and public authorities consider sustainable development aspects during the Permitting process. We will specifically look into how new projects consider the protection of natural habitats and species.

The Permitting phase is particularly important for extractive projects, since it considers what infrastructure will be built, what management practices the company will deploy and how it responds to important legal provisions. The authorities will assess how the project performs according to these provisions, so that projects operate under the best conditions.

While the European Union has about 162,000 nature protected sites¹, as well as an ambitious biodiversity protection policy, it also strives to increase the amount of extracted minerals needed for clean technologies within its own borders. To make sure our future economy is sustainable, we have to safeguard today's natural environment. For new projects, this means being aware of and accounting for adverse effects on wildlife and natural habitats. This, ultimately, forms an important cornerstone for sustainable management in the extractive industry.

It is widely known, and there are examples, that the extractive industry has impacts on species and habitats via its land use change and pollutant emissions. At the same time, rehabilitation of extraction sites has the potential to create new habitats and conserve endangered species. Concludingly, while an active site likely has impacts, a rehabilitated site is able to contribute to biodiversity protection.

The Permitting for these new sites and respective actions to preserve biodiversity has challenges for both public administration and companies. For example, companies struggle to execute exploitation and rehabilitation at the same time or design measures to avoid or off-set impacts. For authorities it is challenging to assess new projects with expertise on both mineral exploitation and nature protection across different legal provisions and departmental borders.

In accordance with a holistic approach towards sustainability, how to best design, as well as assess new projects, should be an integral part for sustainable management in extractive industries. Such approaches should best reflect biodiversity policy on national and European level while making it possible for new projects to take place.

To support such an approach, in this week we put the spotlight on:

- What are the major challenges for both company and policymakers in guaranteeing biodiversity protection in or near protected areas?
- How can companies best anticipate and assess impacts and design preventive measures?
- And what are the ways for public authorities to best assess new projects and guarantee conservation objectives are met in protected areas?

So, we are going to see during this week:

- Detailed background material based on state-of the art research;
- Discussions with high-level experts on their daily work and how they address challenges in innovative companies and effective public administration;
- Insightful case studies that provide a deeper understanding of practical solutions; and
- Short, but interactive, exercises to get to know your peers' perspectives on the topic.

So let us get started.

¹ World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA): The World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA), a joint product of UNEP and IUCN, is the only global database of protected areas (PAs). Collecting information from 65 sources, the georeferenced database covers more than 162,000 PAs in Europe and provides information on names and types of designation, IUCN management categories, locations and extents of PAs and status from "proposed" to "established".

2.7 INTRODUCTION TO SUMEX FOCUS AREA 5: REPORTING

Welcome to the final week of your course.

My name is Anders Forsgren and I work at the sustainability department at Boliden mines. I have a long history in the company, more than 25 years. I have been working with project development, environmental permits and, at the moment, with a focus on social sustainability and community engagement. I am also involved a lot in the development of our sustainability programs and reporting.

In this final week of your course, we will focus on how to report sustainability performance of extraction companies, considering transparency, trust, and effectiveness.

Reporting is the practice of publicly disclosing and communicating economic, environmental, and social performance of a company. Sustainability reporting is crucial for a sustainable business. However, it is not only about collecting data or writing a report – it is about internalizing and improving an organization's commitment to sustainable development. For companies, it increases transparency with stakeholders, improves corporate reputation, and it reduces risks. For local communities impacted by extractive industry, companies need to communicate transparently and report progress in order to build trust.

There is a measure of distrust towards the extractive industry and receiving recognition for the ongoing work is a slow process. To build trust, it is important to use well-established standards for the reporting – but it takes time for the company to establish these and earn recognition by stakeholders. To further facilitate trust, third party audits, open mechanisms to report on all kinds of incoming grievances are important. Another way is to invite local community stakeholders and work together, for example, when it comes to data collection.

While in the late 1990s, corporate sustainability reporting was widely unknown, it has evolved today with high expectations from all types of stakeholders. More than 90% of the largest companies are today publishing sustainability reports.

The most pressing topics to report on differ not only according to timing, but also on the topic, as different stakeholders value different things. Investors, for example, may perceive greenhouse gas emissions, source

utilization, and circular economy as crucial topics on which to report. However, local stakeholders may value employment, procurement opportunities, and the rights of indigenous people as topics on which to report. For the more traditional sustainability aspects, such as Health and Safety, there are well-established metrics and indicators on which to report. For the new focus areas, such as climate, biodiversity, and the ones important to local stakeholders, there are still no established metrics on which to report.

Therefore, it is crucial to follow the development in this quickly evolving field and to know about recent developments on new standards and upcoming metrics.

In this week, we will answer:

- What is the state-of-the-art on sustainability reporting?
- What sustainability topics should be reported for an extractive industry?
- And how does a company conduct their reporting to facilitate transparency, trust, and effectiveness?

In this week, we will inform you about the most recent research findings of the SUMEX project on sustainability reporting in Europe. You will have the opportunity to discuss with high-level experts on the most pressing topics and will test your knowledge in a small exercise. As this is the last week of this course, we will also provide you with a short recap on sustainable management of mineral resource extraction.

I am looking forward to discussing sustainability reporting with you and our experts and really dig down into hands on practical solutions.

2.8 AV STORYTELLING 3

The third storytelling video is currently in preparation. The video will be produced in the start-up phase of the second live run of the MOOC which is planned for August 2023 and will be published during the MOOC promotion campaign. One of the concept ideas for the video is to provide a 'roadshow' of success of the first MOOC live run (i.e. snippets of MOOC expert videos and MOOC interactive learner discussions on the FutureLearn platform).